

EDUCATIONAL TASKS THAT LEAD TO CREATIVE THINKING IN LITERARY EDUCATION

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Annotation . In today's rapidly informed age, it is very important to interest the student in science, especially in fiction, to educate him, to form his spiritual-ethical, educational and literary-aesthetic views from a young age. The reason is that in order to preserve the national image and spirituality of each nation, new pedagogical technologies and assignments are needed to encourage young generations to think independently, to be able to independently understand the meaning of an artistic work, to understand the ideas in the work, and to direct students to creativity. development is more relevant today than ever. This article presents examples of educational tasks that guide students to creative thinking.

Key words : creative thinking, creativity, assignment, creating a story , short classification, labyrinth;

Today, it is more important and relevant than ever to develop students' thinking through literature classes. The role of educational tasks that guide creative thinking in the development of students' thinking and imagination is incomparable.

Creative thinking basically depends on these two things - critical thinking and creativity. Critical thinking is clear and rational thinking. It involves thinking clearly and systematically, following the rules of logic and scientific reasoning, among other things. As for creativity, it means offering new and useful ideas , creating alternative possibilities . Creative thinking is an important skill for today's youth. These skills help them adapt to a world that is constantly and rapidly changing, requiring workers with "21st century" skills that go beyond simple literacy . In general, today's student is expected to work in the future in fields that do not even exist now, to solve new problems through new technologies. Formation of creative thinking skills in students allows them to solve increasingly complex local and global problems through an unusual approach. Therefore, creativity is required from today's teachers in order to cultivate a creative thinking student. The term creativity is defined in this way, creativity (lot, visual "create", "creative" is a social ability that characterizes the readiness of an individual to produce new ideas and is part of talent as an independent factor)

The centuries-old experience of teaching literature shows that the work experience of a person cannot be simply learned and mastered . Maybe it will be born in the course of the lesson. Based on the above ideas, we will make the following observations on the example of 5th grade literature...

It is useful to give the task "Labyrinth proverb" to check the knowledge and creativity of students when passing the topic of proverbs given in the 5th grade literature lesson. Pupils are given brief information about the proverb, task, wise words, and the teacher writes one

proverb on the board. Students are given a task to find a new proverb whose first word begins with the last letter of the proverb. The "Labyrinth Proverb" task will be as follows:

Ilm - dilning chirog'i, Maktab – ilm chorbog'i.

Izzat tilasang, ko'p dema, Sihat tilasang, ko'p yema.

Aytilgan so'z – otilgan o'q.

Sabr tagi – sariq oltin.

Nonsiz yashab bo'lmas, gapni oshab bo'lmas.

So'qir ko'zga surmaning keragi yo'q.

Qozoni boshqaning qayg'usi boshqa.

Aqlli pakana, ahmoq darozdan yaxshi.

Ish bilganga bir tanga, gap bilganga o'n tanga.

Rejali ish – hamisha besh.

Axtargan topar.

Shamol bo'lmasa, daraxtning uchi qimirlamaydi.

At this point, if the proverb does not come out of the letters, it is necessary to give the student the opportunity to write a riddle or a wise word so that the student does not stop thinking. Nature doesn't have a "magic wand" to generate new ideas, but any student can be guided to think creatively and come up with different solutions. As homework, students are asked to create one wise words and get into the maze (you can even draw a maze with a pen). Example: layer by layer there will be a river.

When reading Aesop's fables, the question is asked what are the characters of Aesop's fables. What students say is written on the board. For example, they say wolf, stork, frogs, deer, donkey, eagle, deer, shepherd, hunter and so on. The students will now be given the task to write an independent fairy tale according to your choice. Each student will compose a fairy tale based on this assignment and read it. This assignment is effective in forming students' creative thinking and speaking skills.

Task "Brief description". Students are given a task to describe the characters in the story "Fanorchi Ota". Through this, students will have the opportunity to get to know the image of the characters in the story and their place in the work

QOSIM CHO'LOQ

AHMAD

FANORCHI OTA

are asked to write a comparison of characters on the topic "Ahmad, Kasim Cholak and I" in order to develop their creative thinking ability and evaluate their personal "I".

Ahmad's character	Kasim lame character	Me

In short, by giving students tasks that guide them to creative thinking, their ability to imagine and think grows, and good moral qualities are formed in the student's personality.

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